

**The Norwegian Generations and Gender Survey,
Round 2 - Wave 1 (2020). Documentation of the data
collection process**

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1. Background and study scope

Background

In September 2020, Statistics Norway (SSB) (represented by the Research department of Statistics Norway) and the Central-hub of the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) (represented by the Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute at the Royal Netherland Academy of Arts and Science (NIDI-KNAW)) agreed on to conduct a data collection of the first wave of the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) in Norway. In a service agreement between SSB and GGP, SSB was defined as the data provider, especially responsible to develop a sampling methodology and sample design for the survey in accordance with GGP technical guidelines and for sample management activities including the construction and maintenance of the sample. GGP was defined as the central coordinator, providing support in the pre-fieldwork phase, during the fieldwork and monitoring the fieldwork, as well as to provide data cleaning and checking (harmonization) and dissemination services of the collected data.

The fieldwork for the survey was conducted in November and December 2020 (see details below) and the survey was entitled “Undersøkelse om familie og arbeid” [Survey on family and work] in Norway. The project was funded by the Norwegian Ministry of Children and Families, the Norwegian Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs and the Norwegian Research Council (Project number 300870). In Norway, the project was coordinated by the Research Department of Statistics Norway, in collaboration with the Section for Social Surveys at Statistics Norway and the Department of Sociology and Human Geography at the University of Oslo.

Study scope

The data collection started 20 November 2020 and ended 22 December 2020. The geographic coverage of the data is national and there are no lower geographical units available in the data. Residents in Norway aged 18 to 54 years by the beginning of November 2020 are the target population covered by the data.

2. Methodology and Processing

A gross sample of 15 000 persons aged 18-54 years was established to conduct the Generations and Gender Survey in 2020 in Norway. The sample was based on the Statistic Norway's population database (BeReg), which is continuously updated with information from the Central Population Register of Norway and thus includes all registered residents of the country. By 01. November 2020, 15.000 individuals in the defined age range were randomly (simple random sampling) drawn from this register. At this time, about 2 665 000 men and women in this age range were registered as residents in Norway (<https://www.ssb.no/en/statbank/sq/10054226>). Next, the sample was linked to "The common contact register", which is administrated by the Norwegian Digitalisation Agency (<https://eid.difi.no/en/common-contact-register>). "The common contact register" provides contact information for official authorities. This allows Statistics Norway to contact potential respondents through an approved and valid e-mail and mobile number. In the age group of our sample, more than 95% of all residents have provided a valid e-mail and/or mobile number to "The common contact register". In line with this, 498 respondents (3.3%) of the gross sample could not be contacted by e-mail and thus received an information letter by post. 169 of them could be followed up by one SMS in the data collection period (for details see Table 1).

The aim of the project was to achieve a dataset with about 5 000 valid respondents for this first wave of the GGS. Based on SSBs experience with a web-survey on the quality of life (Pettersen & Støren 2020), which had a response rate of over 40%, it was decided to draw a gross sample with 15 000 individuals for the GGS in Norway.

The survey was designed as a web-survey and was available in Norwegian (bokmål) to the respondents. The standard questionnaire for the first wave of the GGS was translated by the national team with the TMT-software provided by the GGP. The web-survey was programmed by the GGP in Blaise® (www.blaise.com), allowing respondents to fill out the survey online on all kind of personal computers, tablets or mobile phones.

The fieldwork period was in November and December 2020 and during that time Norway was influenced by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. Compared to other European countries, death rates related to COVID-19 were lower in Norway. Overall, no increase in mortality rates was observed in 2020 in Norway. In terms of COVID-19 infection rates, the development in Norway followed more or less the pattern in the rest of Europe, with high numbers of infections in March and April 2020 and declining rates and low rates during the summer 2020. With a strict lockdown introduced on 12 March 2020, the Norwegian Government reacted relatively fast and avoided an overburdening of the healthcare system. In the beginning of November 2020, the number of daily new infections increased again after low numbers in the previous months. As a reaction to that, the Government re-enforced stricter closing and social distancing measures in the time of the fieldwork, especially in the region of Oslo. The "Government Response Index", constructed by the Oxford Covid-19 Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT) in order to provide international comparative data and indicators on COVID-19 related policies, reflects this development (Hale et al., 2020). The Index builds on government responses and containment and closure measures, where 0 indicates "no response" and 100 is the highest value, indicating the strongest possible responses. In the weeks before the fieldwork, the index was below 40

but increased to over 50 during the fieldwork period. With an online survey as the mode for data collection, the COVID-19 situation had no direct impact on the practical aspects of the fieldwork. All contact with respondents could be conducted as planned.

To ensure that the collected data can be used in comparative studies, only few deviations from the baseline questionnaire (Gauthier et al. 2021) have been implemented in this first wave of the Norwegian GGS. To shorten the interview time, optional questions were not included. Due to a mistake in the Blaise-coding, question DEM28c (Intention to marry), was not asked.

Three specific modifications were implemented in agreement with GGP. Based on the GGP-memo on possible Covid-19 questions and the GGS questionnaire (Rijken, Emery & Gauthier 2020), one question with four items related to COVID-19 was implemented in the Norwegian survey: Respondents were asked to compare their life situation now with the situation right before the outbreak of the disease in March 2020, regarding their economic security, their mental health, close relationships and work situation. Next, questions from the proposed sub-module on uncertainties and resilience (Andersson, Dahlberg & Neyer 2020) were included: one question related to global uncertainty (11 sub-items), two questions related to economic uncertainty, two questions regarding personality traits and one question about use of social media. Finally, the experimental GGS module measuring childbearing motives, desires and intentions was implemented (Mynarska & Raybould 2020).

Due to strict budget limitations, the survey could not be tested in a pilot or pre-test with external respondents. To compensate for that, the working group in Norway and affiliated colleagues made extensive pre-tests of the online survey before it was released. Based on these pre-tests, an average response time between 30 to 45 minutes was estimated. As respondents of the online-survey were explicitly informed about the option to answer to the survey in several steps and take a break when necessary (one could continue at the same question where one had stopped, and it was possible to go back to previous questions), exact data on actual average response time are not available.

The documentation for the Norwegian GGS 2020 is released online through the GGP-colectica portal: <http://ggp.colectica.org/>. The exact wording of the questionnaire in Norwegian (bokmål) is available at https://ggpsurvey.ined.fr/documents/Questionnaires/GGP_NOR.blax.

3. Information provided to the respondents and contact protocol

In line with the service agreement between SSB and GGP, SSB was responsible for contact with the respondents. Two websites related to the survey and fieldwork were established, one at Statistics Norway and one at GGP (for screenshots, see Appendix A1 and A2). On these webpages, the purpose and content of the survey was described. Further, it was explained how respondents can answer to the survey and information about the incentive (see below) as well as data protection measures was given. It was also pointed out how respondents may take contact if they experience technical problems and have questions related to the survey. Contact information for the data protection officer at Statistics Norway was also provided on both webpages, while only the webpage at Statistics Norway listed explicitly the contact information for technical/general support and answering hours. During the fieldwork period, the dedicated webpage at SSB was accessed 1.809 times (see Appendix A3).

Ahead of the data collection, the Section for Social Surveys at SSB established a contact plan (see Table 1) with the respondents, to increase the response rate throughout the data collection period. In previous web-surveys conducted by Statistics Norway, most responses were achieved in the first days after a survey was launched. Response analysis show that reminders to participate or to complete the survey can increase the response rate, but only within a certain time frame. After two weeks, additional reminders only led to very limited increase in response rates (Pettersen & Støren 2020; Pettersen 2021). It should be noted, that Statistics Norway has established a policy to contact possible respondent only a limited number of times during a fieldwork. The reasoning behind this policy is to maintain the reputation and trust in the national statistical office. In line with these experiences and this policy, the contact plan displayed in Table 1 was adapted for the fieldwork.

All E-Mails and the letters were sent from SSB and signed by the Director of SSB (see Appendix A4 as an example of the first E-Mail). Text messages were signed with the acronym "SSB" (See Appendix A5 as an example of the first text message). Similar information as on the information webpages was provided in the first E-Mail and letter. The first text message recalled that an E-Mail or letter to participate in the study was send and informed again about the incentive. Follow-up E-Mails and text messages reminded about the survey. The text was somewhat shortened but included still the main purpose of the survey and contact information. In addition, all E-Mails and text messages included a direct and individual link to the web-survey. Thus, it was not necessary for the respondents to memorize and enter their personal ID to participate in the survey (the personal ID was still provided). The letter (mostly identical with the E-Mail displayed in A4) did not include a direct link, but the url of the web-survey and the personal ID, which had to be entered by the respondents manually.

To facilitate the contact with the respondents, the sample was spitted up in six groups, allowing also a variation of the time-point at which a reminder was send out (see Table 1). The first five groups could be contacted by E-Mail and most respondents also by SMS (99.2%), while the last group includes the 498 respondents that were contacted through a letter that was sent by post.

Table 1. Contact plan and actual contacts by e-mail and SMS

			Group 1 (N=2900)	Group 2 (N=2900)	Group 3 (N=2900)	Group 4 (N=2900)	Group 5 (N=2902)	Group 6 (N=498)
Monday, 23.11.20 (Day 1)	First contact	E-Mail	12:00 (2900)	13:00 (2899)	14:00 (2900)	16:00 (2900)	18:00 (2902)	
		SMS	12:30 (2874)	13:30 (2875)	14:30 (2877)	16:30 (2879)	18:30 (2881)	
Wednesday, 25.11.20 (Day 3)	1 st reminder not started	SMS	18:00 (2243)	16:00 (2264)	14:00 (2226)	13:00 (2186)	12:30 (2155)	
Thursday, 26.11.20 (Day 4)	1 st reminder if started	E-Mail	18:00 (335)	14:00 (677)		12:00 (664)		
Friday, 27.11.20 (Day 5)	2 nd reminder not started	E-Mail	12:00 (1948)	12:30 (2029)	13:00 (1993)	13:30 (1965)		
	First contact	Letter						(498)
Monday, 30.11.20 (Day 8)	3 rd reminder not started	E-Mail	14:00 (1809)	18:00 (1886)	16:00 (1846)	12:00 (1851)	13:00 (1870)	
		SMS	14:30 (1783)	18:30 (1867)	16:30 (1827)	12:30 (1830)	13:00 (1851)	
Tuesday, 01.12.20 (Day 9)	2 nd reminder if started	E-Mail	18:00 (450)	12:00 (955)		14:00 (664)		
Friday, 04.12.20 (Day 12)	4 th reminder not started	SMS	12:30 (1604)	13:00 (1627)	12:00 (1608)	14:00 (1611)	13:30 (1599)	
	1 st reminder	SMS						14:30 (169)
Tuesday, 08.12.20 (Day 16)	3 rd reminder if started	SMS	13:00 (492)	18:00 (1026)		16:00 (1013)		
Monday, 14.12.20 (Day 22)	Extra reminder not started	E-Mail	14:00 (1508)					
		SMS	14:00 (1458)					
	4 th reminder if started	SMS				14:30 (3328)		
		E-Mail				14:30 (4336)		
	4 th reminder if almost finished	SMS				14:00 (144)		
		E-Mail				14:00 (145)		

In line with the contact plan, the first group was contacted by E-Mail at 12:00 on the 23. November 2020. Throughout the afternoon, groups 2-5 received similar E-Mails. The same day, this was followed up by a text message send to the mobile phones of the respondents. The last group, without a valid E-Mail address in the “The common contact register”, was contacted by a letter sent out 27. November 2020 (and 169 persons in this group received a follow-up text message one week thereafter).

The web-survey itself was hosted on the serves of NIDI (https://ggp.nidi.nl/ggp_no). The survey was put online by the GGP Central Hub in the morning of the 23. November 2020 and taken offline by the end of the fieldwork period in the afternoon 22. December 2020.

During the field period, the GGP Central Hub extracted every morning from Monday to Friday a data set from the survey, indicating (i) if a respondent clicked on the link, (ii) agreed to participate in the survey, (iii) started the survey (answered to date of birth) or (iv) finished the survey. This information was provided thereafter to the Survey Department of Statistics Norway.

Respondents that finished the survey, were not contacted any longer. In line with the contact plan, respondents that did not finish the survey yet, were either reminded to participate (group that had not started yet) or to complete the survey (group that had started). The text in these reminders was adapted according to this.

After respondents clicked for the first time on the provided link (or had entered the individual ID), they were navigated to the starting page of the web-survey. On this page, respondents were once again informed about the topic of the survey and their rights (GDPR). Finally, they were asked to confirm their consent to participate in the survey and allowing the use of the collected data for research, by ticking of a box (see Appendix A5 for the starting page). Thereafter, the data collection started with the first question (date of birth). If respondents stopped answering to the survey at any point, they could continue where they stopped, when clicking again on the individual link. It was also possible to navigate backwards in the web-survey, if one wanted to change or check answers to previous questions.

Two unplanned deviations from the original contact plan emerged throughout the fieldwork-period. On day 5 of the field work, a planned reminder was not sent out to group 5 while on day 22, an unplanned extra reminder was sent out to group 1. In addition, the survey was not accessible for about 25 hours during fieldwork-period (from 02 December 2020 at 13:00 until 03 December 2020 at 14:00) due to an expired SSL security certificate on the servers of the Royal Netherland Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) of which NIDI is an institute.

During the fieldwork-period, SSB registered 172 contacts with respondents regarding the survey (119 by e-mail and 53 by phone). 53 respondents expressed that they did not want to participate in the survey, 10 refused to participate, 3 expressed that they had no time to participate, 7 expressed concerns related to data protection, 15 had general questions related to the survey, 21 had problems with the web-survey, 14 required a confirmation regarding the survey (no phishing etc.), 20 complained about the quantity of reminders send, while the remaining requests included other topics (including that the survey was not accessible 25 hours). The requests regarding problems with the web-survey itself (at

least 21 requests), were mostly related to survey questions requiring dates, which had to be filled in in a certain format [MM/YYYY].

To increase the response rate, a lottery to win gift cards was introduced as an incentive to potential respondents. In the information provided to the respondents (E-Mail, text messages and the webpage), it was explained that respondents completing the web-survey, will automatically participate in a lottery, giving them the chance to win one of 65 gift cards with a value of 1000 NOK (approx. 100 €) each. The letter explained also, that 15000 persons were invited to participate in the survey. However, no further information on the expected response rate and thus, the expected winning chance, was given. In line with the information given, 65 persons were randomly selected among all complete answers in January 2021 and gift cards were sent out thereafter by Statistics Norway.

4. Survey participation and incoming responses during fieldwork period

Based on the data extracts during the weekdays provided by the GGP central hub to SSB, the participation of the respondents throughout the fieldwork period could be monitored. Figure 1 provides an overview of the incoming responses in percentages of the gross sample. Each respondent can be part of several groups at each time point, e.g., those that completed the survey, have also clicked on it, expressed their consent and started the survey. The blue vertical lines indicate days where reminders were sent out, while the black vertical line indicates the day the survey was not accessible due to the expired SSL security certificate on the servers of NIDI-KNAW.

Figure 1 indicates that each reminder that was sent out, led to an increase in reactions from possible respondents and the response rate: More respondents navigated to the survey webpage and eventually participated in the survey. However, the impact of these reminders declined after two weeks in the field. Next, the different lines indicate drop-offs in each step of the data collection: not all respondents that navigated to the survey webpage (*clicked*), did agree to participate in the survey (*consent*), started to answer to the online questionnaire (*started*) or completed the survey by answering to all questions (*completed*).

Figure 1. Responses during the fieldwork period

Table 2 provides an overview over the distribution of these indicators by the end of the fieldwork period, split up by the different groups from the contact plan. In addition to those respondents that answered to all questions ($N=4556$), 475 incomplete interviews that answered at least to section 3 “Fertility section” in the survey, were kept in the dataset. Most of them answered also to some of the following questions and thus, these data were considered as sufficient for many analyses focusing on the core topics of the GGS.

Table 2. Responses by the end of the fieldwork period

		Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	All
	<i>N</i>	2900	2900	2900	2900	2902	498	15000
Clicked	<i>N</i>	1680	1557	1544	1586	1553	46	7966
	%	57,9	53,7	53,2	54,7	53,5	9,2	53,1
Consent	<i>N</i>	1466	1348	1353	1370	1385	37	6959
	%	50,6	46,5	46,7	47,2	47,7	7,4	46,4
Started	<i>N</i>	1355	1231	1253	1259	1309	33	6440
	%	46,7	42,4	43,2	43,4	45,1	6,6	42,9
Completed	<i>N</i>	966	873	871	895	931	27	4563
	%	33,3	30,1	30,0	30,9	32,1	5,4	30,4
Final dataset								
Complete	<i>N</i>	964	870	871	894	930	27	4556
Partly complete	<i>N</i>	109	89	91	104	82	0	475
Total	<i>N</i>	1073	959	962	998	1012	27	5031
	%	37,00	33,07	33,17	34,14	34,87	5,42	33,54

Note: Taking also in account respondents that rejected to participate later, in total 8032 responses were recorded by GGP, 6 were respondents required to be deleted, 2986 were deleted as they dropped off early in the questionnaire and 9 were deleted because of high number of user missings.

Overall, for the final dataset, the response rate is 33,54% (30,37% with completed interviews). Group 1 has a slightly higher response rate, which seems to be related to the extra reminder that was sent out on day 22, only to respondents in this group and that hadn't started with the survey yet. The final response rates are quite similar for the groups 2 to 5, while the last group, that could only be contacted through a letter and partly with an SMS, has clearly the lowest response rate. A low response rate in the group contacted by letter has also been observed by Statistics Norway in a previous web-survey (Pettersen & Støren 2020).

It must be noted, that the numbers in Table 2 and the tables below are based on the raw data directly available after the survey was conducted. Due to additional steps in the data cleaning process, the number of respondents will be slightly lower in the dataset available for research through the GGP Data Archive (Dommermuth et al. 2021).

5. Non-response analysis and weighting

The sample was drawn randomly from the resident population of Norway in November 2020. Thus, it can be assumed that it is representative for the population of Norway at that time. However, if the participation in the survey is not equal across certain characteristics, this can lead to a biased net sample. Non-response weights were developed to address such a non-response bias.

Table 3 presents the distribution across main socio-demographic characteristics for the total sample size (gross sample) and the final dataset (net sample). In face-to-face or telephone interviews, usually some data on reasons for non-response - including explicit refusals, death, wrong address or emigration – are collected. This is usually not possible in web-surveys. About 63 respondents contacted Statistics Norway directly and expressed that they did not want to participate in the survey. Due to the low and non-systematic number of these explicit refusals or withdrawals, Table 3 does not separate between the sample and a gross sample without such refusals, but only between the gross-sample and the net sample, e.g., the final dataset, when calculating response rates and weights.

Different socio-demographic characteristics were linked from different administrative registers (including the Population Register and the National Database on Education) to the sample, in order to analyse the non-response and to calculate non-response weights. However, it is important to note that these register-based data were never connected to the collected survey data. They were only used to calculate weights and all contact information are kept strictly separated and may only be used to establish a new contact plan for a second wave of the Norwegian GGS. Respondents were informed that only information directly provided by them in the web-survey are included in the final dataset.

The difference between then net- and gross-sample (and response rate) is largest when comparing men/women and highest level of education. As the response rate among women is over 11% higher than among men, this led to a difference of 8.3% between the gross and net sample regarding this characteristic. In the previous GGS in Norway, based on a computer-assisted telephone interview, the response-rate for men and women was more similar and the difference between the gross and net sample for women (men) was 0.5% (Lappegård & Veenstra 2010). In two recent web-surveys conducted by Statistics Norway, the non-response rate among men was also lower than among women. In a study on life quality conducted, the difference between the gross and net sample regarding gender was 1.7% (Pettersen & Støren 2020), while it was 7.4% in a survey on rental housing market (Pettersen 2021).

Table 3. Gross-sample, net-sample, response rate by socio-demographic characteristics. Norwegian GGS 2020

	Gross sample		Net sample		Difference: net sample - gross sample	Response rate
	N	%	N	%		%
Sex						
Men	7704	51,4	2164	43,0	-8,3	28,1
Women	7296	48,6	2867	57,0	8,3	39,3
Age						
1: 18-24	2547	17,0	840	16,7	-0,3	33,0
2: 25-29	2112	14,1	692	13,8	-0,3	32,8
3: 30-34	2172	14,5	707	14,1	-0,4	32,6
4: 35-39	1996	13,3	619	12,3	-1,0	31,0
5: 40-44	1988	13,3	670	13,3	0,1	33,7
6: 45-49	2104	14,0	724	14,4	0,4	34,4
7: 50-54	2081	13,9	779	15,5	1,6	37,4
Highest level of education						
ISCED97 0-2: Primary and lower secondary + missing	4128	27,5	782	15,5	-12,0	18,9
ISCED97 3-4: Upper secondary and post-secondary non-tertiary education	5220	34,8	1592	31,6	-3,2	30,5
ISCED97 5: First stage of tertiary education	3941	26,3	1793	35,6	9,4	45,5
ISCED97 6: Second stage of tertiary education	1711	11,4	864	17,2	5,8	50,5
Region						
Oslo	2250	15,0	797	15,8	0,8	35,4
Rogaland	1403	9,4	463	9,2	-0,2	33,0
Møre og Romsdal	707	4,7	232	4,6	-0,1	32,8
Nordland	624	4,2	206	4,1	-0,1	33,0
Viken	3404	22,7	1136	22,6	-0,1	33,4
Innlandet	904	6,0	294	5,8	-0,2	32,5
Vestfold og Telemark	1100	7,3	354	7,0	-0,3	32,2
Agder	837	5,6	251	5,0	-0,6	30,0
Vestland	1770	11,8	606	12,0	0,2	34,2
Trøndelag	1321	8,8	461	9,2	0,4	34,9
Troms og Finnmark	680	4,5	231	4,6	0,1	34,0
Centrality index						
1 – biggest cities/most central	3204	21,4	1154	22,9	1,6	36,0
2	3907	26,0	1341	26,7	0,6	34,3
3	3748	25,0	1232	24,5	-0,5	32,9
4	2301	15,3	754	15,0	-0,4	32,8
5	1249	8,3	358	7,1	-1,2	28,7
6 – small municipalities / rural	591	3,9	192	3,8	-0,1	32,5

Regarding highest level of education, the response rate is 18.9% among those with a primary or lower/lower secondary education (including also 913 respondents without a registered education in the National Database for Education, thus most likely immigrants). This leads to a difference of -12.0% between the net- and gross sample. Response rates increase with highest level of education.

Table 3 also shows some differences in the response rate by age, with the highest response rate among the oldest respondents in the sample (50-54 years, 37.4% response rate) and the lowest among those ages 35-39 years (31.0%).

Based on some additional data provided by GGP, SSB made a descriptive analysis to get a better understanding on when respondents dropped off (or completed the survey). Table 4 describes the participation rate by socio-demographic characteristics at the following steps: clicked on the link and accessed the starting page, agreed to participate (consent), started answering (gender and age), started the partnership section, started the household grid or started life satisfaction section (wel08). Note that the final response rate is somewhat higher than the proportion that answered the wellbeing question, as also respondents that completed at least “Section 3 Fertility” of the survey, were kept in the final dataset (see Table 2).

The table shows that the differences by the available socio-demographic characteristics are quite consistent over time. Table 3 indicates deviations in the final response rate by sex, age and highest level of education. Table 4 shows that the difference between men and women is stable in all the different steps (from “clicking” to “final response rate”). Regarding age, we observe the lowest response rate for those aged 35-39 years. Interestingly, this group reacted as other age groups in the beginning (clicked on the link), but the proportion that continued declined more in the next steps and the proportion that dropped-off in this age group was also higher than other age groups in the step from the partnership-history to the household section. Opposite to this, the oldest age group seems to have the lowest drop-off rate in all steps after clicking on the survey and thus emerges as the group with the highest response rate at the end. Regarding highest level of education, the response rate was lowest for those with a primary or missing education. The difference is already evident in the first step (clicked) and increases in the second (consent), but remained relatively stable thereafter.

Table 4. Participation, drop-off and final response rate by socio-demographic characteristics (in %)

	Clicked	Consent	Started	Partnership history	Start household	Life satisfaction	Final response rate
All	53,11	46,39	42,93	39,53	33,59	31,35	33,54
Sex							
Men	47,09	40,77	37,73	34,11	28,13	26,01	28,09
Women	59,46	52,33	48,42	45,24	39,36	36,98	39,30
Age							
1: 18-24	49,23	44,44	41,11	36,95	32,98	28,98	32,98
2: 25-29	48,63	42,85	40,10	36,51	32,81	30,21	32,77
3: 30-34	52,16	44,84	42,13	37,8	32,55	29,97	32,55
4: 35-39	52,05	44,34	41,38	38,08	31,06	29,01	31,01
5: 40-44	54,73	47,84	44,16	40,85	33,75	32,04	33,70
6: 45-49	57,75	49,62	45,48	42,3	34,46	33,27	34,41
7: 50-54	58,15	51,32	46,61	44,88	37,63	36,47	37,43
Highest level of education							
ISCED97 0-2+ miss.	41,88	32,24	27,33	23,89	19,06	16,84	18,94
ISCED97 3-4	49,90	43,51	40,13	37,07	30,56	28,37	30,5
ISCED97: 5	62,95	57,85	55,16	51,43	45,5	43,11	45,5
ISCED97: 6	67,27	62,95	60,96	57,33	50,5	48,33	50,5
Region							
Oslo	53,42	47,42	44,22	40,18	35,42	33,2	35,42
Rogaland	52,82	46,19	42,48	38,77	33,07	30,36	33,00
Møre og Romsdal	53,89	45,69	41,73	39,32	32,81	30,83	32,81
Nordland	55,13	48,72	44,07	39,9	33,01	31,57	33,01
Viken	52,94	46,45	42,89	39,54	33,52	30,82	33,37
Innlandet	51,99	45,24	42,15	38,83	32,52	30,42	32,52
Vestfold og Telemark	50,91	43,36	40,45	37,45	32,36	30,27	32,18
Agder	50,06	42,77	38,35	36,8	29,99	27,6	29,99
Vestland	54,86	47,68	44,92	40,85	34,24	32,32	34,24
Trøndelag	55,49	48,30	44,06	41,03	34,9	33,31	34,90
Troms og Finnmark	50,44	45,59	43,38	40,00	33,97	31,47	33,97
Centrality index							
1 biggest cities/most central	54,56	48,6	45,44	41,29	36,08	33,61	36,02
2	54,34	48,33	43,82	40,44	34,4	32,15	34,32
3	51,65	45,60	41,92	38,79	32,92	30,5	32,87
4	53,37	45,89	42,5	39,29	32,81	30,55	32,77
5	49,96	41,47	38,43	35,39	28,66	27,22	28,66
6 small municipalities / rural	51,95	45,69	41,12	38,24	32,49	30,96	32,49

To address these biases in the response rates and differences between the gross- and net sample, non-response weights were created. In a first step, logistic regression models were conducted. A dummy variable indicating if a respondent is part of the final dataset or not, served as the dependent variable and the socio-demographic characteristics (see Table 5) were included as the dependent variables. Different combinations, including interaction terms between the dependent variables, were tested. The final model can be described as follows:

*Table 5. Logistic regression model.
Response / Non-Response to the Norwegian GGS 2020*

	DF	Wald-Chi	Pr>Chi
Sex	1	92.45	<.0001
Age groups	6	23.37	0.0007
Education	3	557.70	<.0001
Region	10	9.54	0.4813
Centrality	5	12.51	0.0284
Age*Education	18	29.47	0.0429
Sex*Age	6	19.19	0.0038
Sex*Education	3	6.59	0.0861

N=15.000.

The sampling weights were then calibrated to the gross sample totals corresponding to the variables and interaction terms present in the model (the R-package ReGenesees was used for this purpose). Thus, when running a frequency table including the non-response weight, the gross sample totals are exactly reproduced for any of these variables and interactions. For variables, or combinations of variables, not used in the calibration, the frequency distribution will not equal the gross sample distribution, but for variables related to the calibration variables, it will in general be similar. The average value for the non-response weights is 2.98, reflecting the response-rate of 33% to the survey. The value of the non-response weight varies from about 1.25 to 8.0 (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Histogram of the non-response weight for the Norwegian GGS 2020.

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Appendix

A1. Information webpage at GGP

www.ggp-i.org/norway

GGP Norge: Undersøkelsen om familie og arbeid

Fortell oss din historie!

Du har blitt invitert av Statistisk sentralbyrå (SSB) til å delta i undersøkelsen om familie og arbeid. Undersøkelsen er den norske utgaven av den internasjonale Generations and Gender Survey (GGS). Hovedmålet med undersøkelsen er å få bedre forståelse av familiedannelse og andre hendelser gjennom livsløpet til enkeltpersoner. Det vil gjøre det mulig for forskere å gi innsikt og svar på aktuelle samfunnsmessige og offentlige politiske utfordringer i Norge og i de fleste andre europeiske land. I Norge er du en av 15 000 personer i alderen 18 til 54 år som er tilfeldig trukket fra Folkeregisteret av SSB til å svare på undersøkelsen. Dine svar er et viktig bidrag til ny relevant forskning rundt temaene arbeid og familie, levekår, parforhold, samspill mellom generasjoner og holdninger. Derfor ber vi deg om å delta i vår undersøkelse og at du deler din og din families livshistorie med oss. Vi kommer også til å spørre deg om dine personlige meninger om viktige sosiale spørsmål. Det tar omtrent 40 minutter å delta i undersøkelsen. Du kan ta en pause underveis og fortsette på et senere tidspunkt der du slapp sist, ved å fylle inn ditt bruker-ID igjen.

Opplysningene dine er sikre hos oss

SSB gjennomfører denne undersøkelsen i samarbeid med Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institut (NIDI), som er prosjektkoordinator for GGS. Slik sikrer vi at de ulike nasjonale undersøkelsene er utformet likt og åpner dermed opp for forskning og analyser som sammenligner resultatene på tvers av landene. Både SSB og NIDI garanterer for at dine data blir behandlet i samsvar med den norske statistikkloven og personopplysningsloven samt EUs Personvernforordning. Vi vil ikke knytte personopplysningene dine og kontaktinformasjonen din til svarene dine. Datamaterialet som samles inn, brukes kun til forskning og er kun tilgjengelige for autoriserte forskere ved godkjente forskningsinstitusjoner. Dataene vil brukes for statistiske sammenligninger, som gjennomsnittsverdier, fordelinger og korrelasjoner. Det vil aldri bli offentliggjort svar fra den enkelte deltaker. Mer informasjon om databehandlingen finner du her www.ssb.no/GGP-svar. Har du spørsmål om personvern, kan du sende en e-post til personvernombud@ssb.no eller lese mer på www.ssb.no/omssb/personvern.

Generations and Gender Programme

I Norge blir undersøkelsen finansiert av Barne- og Familiedepartementet, Arbeids- og Sosialdepartementet og Norges Forskningsråd. Som nevnt, er undersøkelsen om familie og arbeid den norske utgaven av den internasjonale Generations and Gender Survey, som blir utviklet av Generations and Gender Programme. Videoen (på engelsk) nedenfor gir en kort innføring i programmet. I tillegg finner mer informasjon om GGS og GGP her på www.ggp-i.org.

A2. Information webpage at Statistics Norway

<https://www.ssb.no/GGP-svar>

<https://www.ssb.no/innrapportering/personer-og-husholdning/ggp-svar>

 Statistisk sentralbyrå
Statistics Norway

ENGLISH COOKIES OG PERSONVERN STIKKORD A-Å KONTAKT OSS

SØK

> STATISTIKK > FORSKNING > **INNRAPPORTERING** > OM SSB > MITT SSB

Forsiden > Innrapportering > Personer og husholdning > GGP-svar

Pågå

Undersøkelse om familie og arbeid

Om rapporteringen

Statistisk sentralbyrå (SSB) gjennomfører nå en webundersøkelse om familie og arbeid i ulike faser av livet. Denne undersøkelsen vil gi oss mer kunnskap om hvordan folk lever sine liv i Norge i dag og hvilke planer de har for fremtiden.

Undersøkelsen vil også kunne lære oss mer om relasjoner, både mellom generasjoner og innad i parforhold. Undersøkelsen er finansiert av Norges forskningsråd, Arbeids- og sosialdepartementet og Barne- og familiedepartementet.

15 000 personer i alderen 18 til 54 år er tilfeldig trukket fra Folkeregisteret til å svare på undersøkelsen.

Hva skal du svare på?

I undersøkelsen spør vi om

- din familie, helse og arbeidssituasjon
- ditt forhold til dine foreldre
- ditt parforhold
- din sosiale kontakt med familie og venner
- hvor fornøyd du er med ulike aspekter av livet ditt
- hverdagslivet ditt og dine planer for fremtiden
- dine holdninger og verdier

En rekke europeiske land gjennomfører undersøkelsen som en del av en internasjonal undersøkelse (Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)). Dataene som blir samlet inn, blir utelukkende brukt til forskningsformål. Du kan finne mer informasjon om undersøkelsen [her](#).

Vi planlegger en oppfølging av denne undersøkelsen i løpet av de neste fire årene. Alle som deltar nå, kan bli kontaktet igjen innen utgangen av 2024.

Howdan svarer du?

Du svarer på undersøkelsen ved å fylle ut et elektronisk spørreskjema. Du har fått tilsendt en lenke og bruker-ID både på e-post og SMS.

Når du klikker på lenken, får du opp skjemaet på websiden for den internasjonale undersøkelsen

KONTAKT

Svartjeneste for personundersøkelser
E-post: sva@ssb.no
Telefon: [62 88 56 08](tel:62885608)
Telefontid: Man - tor: 09 - 21. Fre: 9 - 15

LOVER OG REGLER

[Personvern](#)

Det tar ca. 40 minutter å svare på undersøkelsen. For noen vil det ta kortere tid, for andre noe lenger, avhengig av din familie- og livssituasjon.

Du kan ta en pause underveis og fortsette på et senere tidspunkt. Du logger på igjen med bruker-ID.

Alle som fullfører undersøkelsen vil automatisk delta i trekningen av 65 gavekort på 1 000 kroner.

Opplever du tekniske problemer?

Skjemaet skal fungere på alle nettleisere og alle enheter (mobil, PC, nettbrett). Hvis du opplever tekniske problemer, kan det være lurt å prøve en annen nettleser eller enhet.

Hvis de tekniske problemene ikke løser seg, kan du ta kontakt med oss på

- e-post: svaer@ssb.no
- telefon: 62 88 51 90

Svarene dine er viktige

Vi trenger svar fra alle som er trukket ut, og vi kan ikke erstatte deg med en annen dersom du ikke deltar. Det er frivillig å delta i undersøkelsen, men svarene dine vil bidra til bedre kunnskap om folks familie- og livssituasjon i ulike faser av livet i Norge i dag.

Dataene fra undersøkelsen vil bli brukt i forskning på viktige livsfaser som samliv og barnefødsler, kombinasjon av arbeid og familieliv, og omsorg for barn og eldre. Hvilke valg vi tar, har langsiktige konsekvenser for egen og andres livskvalitet. Det vil også ha konsekvenser for fremtiden til samfunnet vårt. Med de endringene som skjer i befolkningen, trenger politikerne, beslutningstakere og offentligheten kunnskap om hvordan de kan tilrettelegge samfunnet slik at det blir bedre for innbyggerne, både nå og i fremtiden. Dataene som vi samler inn, vil bidra til å forbedre kunnskapsgrunnlaget.

Opplysningene dine er sikre hos oss

SSB kontakter deg for at du skal delta i undersøkelsen, men vi kan ikke knytte personopplysningene dine og kontaktinformasjonen din til svarene dine.

SSB vil aldri dele personopplysningene dine, og alle som arbeider i SSB har taushetsplikt.

Du kan når som helst trekke deg og be om at svarene dine blir slettet.

Det elektroniske spørreskjemaet er laget av den internasjonale undersøkelsen, Generations and Gender Programme (GGP). Ingen personopplysninger blir lagret sammen med data fra spørreskjemaet.

Svarene dine blir bare brukt til forskning og dataene er bare tilgjengelige for autoriserte og godkjente forskere med vitenskapelige formål.

Helt adskilt fra svarene dine, oppbevarer SSB fødselsnummer og kontaktinformasjon fra alle deltakerne fram til 31. desember 2024. Denne informasjon blir bare brukt for å

- kontakte de som har vunnet gavekort
- kontakte deg på nytt i forbindelse med en mulig oppfølging av undersøkelsen innen 2024
- slette svarene dine hvis du ønsker å trekke deg fra undersøkelsen

Undersøkelsen blir gjennomført i samsvar med statistikkloven og personopplysningsloven. Har du spørsmål om personvern, kan du sende en e-post til personvernombud@ssb.no eller lese mer på www.ssb.no/omssb/personvern.

A3. Daily visits by device to the survey information webpage at Statistics Norway (see Appendix A2).

Date	Total	PC	Phone	Tablet
23.11.2020	938	129	757	12
24.11.2020	152	41	99	2
25.11.2020	108	20	79	0
26.11.2020	48	8	41	0
27.11.2020	92	28	51	0
28.11.2020	8	5	5	0
29.11.2020	16	5	15	0
30.11.2020	142	25	107	0
01.12.2020	54	28	28	0
02.12.2020	17	8	15	0
03.12.2020	20	5	12	0
04.12.2020	56	10	48	0
05.12.2020	11	0	10	0
06.12.2020	9	0	7	0
07.12.2020	16	7	10	0
08.12.2020	36	3	36	0
09.12.2020	8	2	3	0
10.12.2020	6	0	5	0
11.12.2020	5	0	7	0
12.12.2020	3	0	0	0
13.12.2020	3	0	2	0
14.12.2020	30	8	13	0
15.12.2020	10	0	10	0
16.12.2020	8	3	3	0
17.12.2020	5	0	3	0
18.12.2020	3	3	0	0
19.12.2020	0	0	0	0
20.12.2020	1	0	0	0
21.12.2020	3	2	0	0
22.12.2020	1	0	2	0
Total	1809	340	1368	14

A4. First contact E-Mail sent to the respondents

GGP <<ioNr>>

Til <<navn>>

Hei.

Statistisk sentralbyrå (SSB) gjennomfører nå en webundersøkelse om familie og arbeid i ulike faser av livet, og du er trukket ut til å delta. Undersøkelsen skal gi oss mer kunnskap om hvordan folk lever i Norge i dag, hvilke planer de har for fremtiden og om befolkningens verdier og holdninger knyttet til disse temaene. En rekke europeiske land gjennomfører undersøkelsen som en del av en internasjonal undersøkelse (Generations and Gender Programme (GGP)). Dataene som blir samlet inn, blir utelukkende brukt til forskningsformål.

Klikk her for å svare på undersøkelsen

[<<XX_individualID_XX>>](https://ggp.nidi.nl/ggp_no/XX_individualID_XX)

Lenken logger deg automatisk inn. Hvis du blir bedt om å oppgi bruker-ID, skriv inn følgende:

Bruker-ID: <<XX_individualID_XX>>

Alle som fullfører undersøkelsen, vil automatisk delta i trekningen av 65 gavekort på 1 000 kroner.

Svarene dine er viktige

Du er en av 15 000 personer i alderen 18-54 år som er tilfeldig trukket ut fra Folkeregisteret til å delta. Du skal svare på spørsmål om deg selv, de du bor sammen med og om foreldrene dine. Det er frivillig å delta, men svarene dine vil bidra til at vi får bedre kunnskap om folks familie- og livssituasjon i ulike livsfaser.

Du kan lese mer om undersøkelsen <https://www.ssb.no/ggp-svar> og om Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) <https://www.ggp-i.org/norway/>

Opplysningene dine er sikre hos oss

Svarene dine blir ikke knyttet opp mot personopplysningene dine, og dataene som samles inn blir bare brukt til forskning av autoriserte forskningsinstitutter. Enkelt svar vil aldri bli offentliggjort. Du kan når som helst trekke deg og be om at opplysningene om deg blir slettet. Det gjør du ved å ringe 62885608 eller sende en e-post til svaer@ssb.no.

SSB oppbevarer fødselsnummer og kontaklinformasjon til alle deltakere fram til 31. desember 2024. Dette blir oppbevart separat fra svarene som er gitt. Informasjonen blir brukt til å kontakte de som har vunnet gavekort, for å kontakte deg på nytt hvis det blir en oppfølging av undersøkelsen innen 2024 og for å slette svarene dine hvis du ønsker å trekke deg fra undersøkelsen.

Kontakt oss på

e-post: sva@ssb.no

telefon: 62 88 56 08

Svartjenesten er åpen kl. 09-21 mandag til torsdag og 10-15 fredag.

Med vennlig hilsen

Geir Axelsen

administrerende direktør

A5. First text message sent to respondents

Hei <<NAME>>. Du er trukket ut til å delta i undersøkelsen om familie og arbeid. En invitasjon er sendt til deg på e-post. Trykk på https://ggp.nidi.nl/ggp_no/XX_IndividualID_XX for å svare. Alle som fullfører undersøkelsen, er med i trekningen av 65 gavekort på 1 000 kroner. Du kan lese mer om undersøkelsen på <https://www.ssb.no/ggp-svar>. Kontakt oss på e-post svaer@ssb.no eller telefon 62 88 51 90 dersom du har spørsmål. Vennlig hilsen SSB

A6. Text of the starting page of the web-survey (asking for consent to participate)

Denne undersøkelsen handler om familie, arbeid og dagligliv. Dine svar vil hjelpe oss med å forstå dagens familier og hva folk må håndtere i ulike faser av livet. Din deltakelse er frivillig, og du kan når som helst trekke deg og kreve at opplysningene om deg blir slettet. Dette gjør du ved å ringe svartjenesten vår på 62885608 eller sende en e-post til svar@ssb.no. Hvis du ikke ønsker å svare på ett eller flere av spørsmålene, står du fritt til å hoppe over de det gjelder. Undersøkelsen er en del av den internasjonale undersøkelsen Generations and Gender Programme og gjennomføres i samarbeid med Netherlands Interdisciplinary Demographic Institute (NIDI). Dine data blir behandlet i samsvar med den norske statistikkloven og personopplysningsloven samt EUs Personvernforordning. Videre informasjon finner du under <https://www.ssb.no/GGP-svar>. Svarene dine vil kun bli brukt til forskning og vil kun være tilgjengelige for autoriserte og godkjente forskere med vitenskapelige formål. Forskningsdataene vil ikke inneholde personopplysninger eller kontaktinformasjon.

Før vi begynner, vil vi gjerne at du aktivt bekrefter din deltakelse i undersøkelsen: Jeg samtykker til å delta i «Undersøkelsen om familie og arbeid» og bekrefter at mine svar kan brukes til vitenskapelige formål.